

MORPHOLOGICAL AND PHYSIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF GRAPE BUSH ORGANS

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In the cultivated state, grapevines are cultivated with various bush formations, using special agricultural techniques (pruning, garters, operations with green parts, etc.). Depending on the functions performed, vegetative (root, stem, leaves) and generative (bud, inflorescence, flower, berry and seeds) organs are distinguished.

Vegetative organs perform the function of plant life support. They absorb and move water, as well as nutrients, important metabolic processes occur in them (photosynthesis, respiration, etc.). These formations perform the function of growth, vegetative reproduction, etc.

Generative (reproductive) organs perform the function of sexual reproduction. Their development in a grape plant ends with the formation of edible berries.

Depending on the location in relation to the soil surface, the organs of grape bushes are conventionally divided into aboveground and underground.

Organography (description of external form), anatomy (internal structure) and physiology (phenomena of life) of the grape plant are considered in the process of growth and development of all its main organs.

Organography. Depending on the method of reproduction, grape roots can be of different origins. In seed reproduction, they arise from the embryonic root of the seed and are called taproot, in vegetative reproduction, they are formed endogenously and are called adventitious.

The root system is a set of roots of one plant. Its type is determined by the ratio of the growth of the main, lateral and adventitious roots (Fig. 2.3). With the predominant growth of the main root, a taproot system is formed (characteristic of seedlings), with the predominant development of a large number of adventitious roots, a fibrous root system (characteristic of grape seedlings).

The taproot, emerging from the germinating seed, is directed vertically into the soil. Soon, under the root collar, branches of lateral roots of the first order arise, which originate in the root-bearing layer-pericycle as a result of increased cell division. From the lateral roots of the first order, roots of the

second order begin to develop, from them - the third and so on up to the sixth order. These branches together constitute the root system..

Fig. 1. The root system of grapes

a-taproot: 1-taproot; 2-lateral branches; b-fibrous, formed by roots grown from a cutting: 1-dew roots; 2-middle; 3-heel

The root system formed in the cutting is fibrous. On the cutting, which turns into an underground trunk (root trunk), connecting the root system with the above-ground part of the bush, adventitious roots are formed from the pericycle, from them lateral roots of the 1st order depart, on which lateral roots of the 2nd order are formed, and so on up to the 6th and higher order, depending on soil conditions, climate, age of the bush and other factors. In both cases, the roots of the last orders are feeding. They remain white for a very long time and only at the end of summer gradually become covered with cork tissue, and in the fall they mostly die off. Thus, the root system consists of old skeletal roots, which firmly anchor the plant in the soil, and young roots capable of absorbing water, mineral salts and carbon dioxide from the soil. Skeletal roots are usually long, fleshy, uniformly thickened, covered on the outside with a thin layer of crust that separates annually. They are conductors of water and nutrients, they synthesize organic substances and store reserve nutrients. The degree of development of the main roots and the completeness of their overgrowth with feeding roots determines the power of the root system, which

is directly dependent on the total area of the absorbing (sucking) surface. The roots of a grape plant can penetrate to a great depth (2-6 m, sometimes about 14 m) and spread horizontally, usually beyond the area of nutrition provided to them. Depending on the place of appearance along the length of the rootstock, the roots have different names. In the upper part near the soil surface, the so-called dew (superficial) roots develop, usually thin, short, poorly developed, many of which die off by autumn. If they are not removed in time, they can develop strongly to the detriment of others, which will make the bush vulnerable to frost or drought. The roots that developed from the former nodes of the middle part of the underground trunk are called middle (lateral), and from its lower part (heel) - heel. The task of the winegrower is to promote the development of these roots, since they serve as the basis for the vital activity of the plant.

A young root is distinguished by:

- a tip (growth cone), covered with a root cap;
- a growth zone - very delicate, white, 2-5 mm long, where the formation and division of cells occurs;
- an absorption zone - also white, densely covered with root hairs that enter into exchange reactions with the soil absorption complex, the length of this zone is 1-2 cm;
- a conductive zone - yellow (brown), which is associated with the occurrence of mechanical tissue intercutis (Fig. 2.4).

Root cap - a formation in the form of a cone-shaped cap that covers and protects the delicate cells of the tip and partially the growth zone of the taproot and adventitious (adventitious) roots from mechanical damage when they are introduced into the substrate. This is the organ of geotropic orientation of the root.

The root cap of grapes is sharp, hard, yellow, and brown in aerial roots. It consists of several strong thick layers of tightly adjacent cells. The outer cells loosen, dry out and fall off, thereby facilitating the movement of the root in the soil, and the inner cells are constantly formed from the cells of the growth cone. Root hairs are elongated processes, outgrowths of the cells of the surface tissue (epidermis) in the root absorption zone. They arise only from the outer cell wall. The number of root hairs on the root depends on the soil moisture and the order of its branching. Thus, in dry soil there are more of them (more than 1 thousand per 1 mm² of the surface of the absorption zone) than in wet soil (several hundred per 1 mm²). On the roots of lower orders of branching there are more

root hairs (since these roots have a longer absorption zone). In rapidly growing roots, the hairs die off after 1-2 days, then new ones are formed. Thus, the absorption zone is constantly at a distance of 2-5 mm from the root apex.

In warm and humid weather, dew (superficial) roots appear at the soil surface, which should be removed.

The main function of the root, which has a primary anatomical structure, is the absorption of water and nutrients dissolved in it from the soil. As it grows and develops, the root begins to perform additional functions - to serve as a means of conducting absorbed water and nutrients, and to act as a storage organ. Therefore, it is rebuilt (Fig. 2). The transition of the root to a secondary anatomical structure begins with the formation of cambium.

Fig. 2. The terminal part of the grape root (according to Negrul)

a - cap; b - growth zone; c - absorption zone; g - conducting zone; b - small roots

Under the areas of the primary phloem, groups of dividing cells are isolated, which spread to the sides and form a curved arc of cambium, resting on the pericycle. Somewhat later, the cells of the pericycle, dividing, form cambium above the bundles of primary wood. The cambium areas under the phloem and above the xylem close, forming a solid ring, initially shaped like an asterisk. Cambium deposits secondary bast cells to the periphery and secondary wood cells to the center, ensuring the development of secondary anatomical structure

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